

Bayesian Hierarchical Models and the Maximum Entropy Principle

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Abstract

Bayesian hierarchical models are frequently used in practical data analysis contexts. One interpretation of these models is that they provide an indirect way of assigning a prior for unknown parameters, through the introduction of hyperparameters. The resulting marginal prior for the parameters (integrating over the hyperparameters) is usually dependent, so that learning one parameter provides some information about the others. In this contribution, I will demonstrate that, when the prior given the hyperparameters is a canonical distribution (a maximum entropy distribution with moment constraints), the dependent marginal prior also has a maximum entropy property, with a different constraint. This constraint is on the *marginal distribution* of some function of the unknown quantities. The results shed light on what information is actually being assumed when we assign a hierarchical model.

1. INTRODUCTION

Consider a collection of unknown quantities

$$\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\} \quad (1)$$

for which we want to assign a joint probability distribution. These quantities could be data values that will eventually become known, or they might be parameters — the important thing is that they are currently unknown. A simple choice of prior that describes a large amount of ignorance is the uniform prior,

$$\pi(\mathbf{x}) \propto 1, \quad (2)$$

defined over some suitably wide domain of possible values of \mathbf{x} . However, when considering some functions $T_i = f_i(\mathbf{x})$ that are of particular interest, the prior for the T values implied by π is often unsuitable. If the expected values of the $\{T_i\}$ are specified (somehow), the prior may be updated to take into account this constraint using the principle of maximum entropy [1, 2, 3], giving the well-known result

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{\pi(\mathbf{x}) \exp(\sum_i \lambda_i f_i(\mathbf{x}))}{Z(\boldsymbol{\lambda})}. \quad (3)$$

The values of the λ s need to be selected so as to enforce the desired values of $\langle T_i \rangle$. The result is the ‘canonical’ family of distributions from statistical mechanics [4].

However, it would be unusual for expected values (which are properties of the probability distribution, not of \mathbf{x}) to really be ‘known’. If they are unknown, it is tempting to use the canonical distribution of Equation 3 as if it were the distribution *conditional* on those expected values only. A marginal distribution for the expected values would complete the model specification, and the resulting marginal prior for \mathbf{x} could be found by integrating out the hyperparameter. This marginal distribution would be a mixture of canonical distributions. However, the maximum entropy interpretation is apparently lost, because a mixture of canonical distributions is not itself a canonical distribution. The purpose of this paper is to clarify that a maximum entropy interpretation of the marginal prior for \mathbf{x} does in fact exist, and to identify what the effective constraint is.

2. BAYESIAN HIERARCHICAL MODELS

In a Bayesian inference context, a prior distribution for a collection of quantities \mathbf{x} would often be assigned hierarchically, especially when there is prior information connecting the $\{x_i\}$ together. With the introduction

of hyperparameters α , the prior is defined in two stages, with a prior $p(\alpha)$ for the hyperparameters and then a conditional prior $p(\mathbf{x} | \alpha)$ for the parameters given the hyperparameters. The conditional prior is often the product of n ‘iid’ distributions, one for each of the x s:

$$p(\mathbf{x} | \alpha) = \prod_{i=1}^n p(x_i | \alpha). \quad (4)$$

The implied marginal prior for \mathbf{x} can be found by integrating over the hyperparameters:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \int p(\alpha) p(\mathbf{x} | \alpha) d\alpha \quad (5)$$

$$= \int p(\alpha) \prod_{i=1}^n p(x_i | \alpha) d\alpha. \quad (6)$$

Such a choice is often justified by exchangeability — when the $\{x_i\}$ values need to be treated interchangeably, the hierarchical construction guarantees it. In the limit of large n , the argument also works the other way around, in that the joint distribution for any exchangeable sequence of quantities $\{x_i\}$ can be expressed as in Equation 6. However, since the principle of maximum entropy is rarely invoked in justifying such a choice, it is unclear whether there is any connection between the maximum entropy principle and the choice of the hierarchical model.

3. MAXIMUM ENTROPY CONSTRAINTS

The most common type of constraint used in maximum entropy is constraints on expected values. However, in principle, any constraint on the probability distribution (so-called *testable information*) can be used [6]. Here, we will identify the implicit constraint that leads to results like Equation 6 for the updated maximum entropy distribution for \mathbf{x} .

Consider a prior $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ and suppose that some function of \mathbf{x} , written as $T = f(\mathbf{x})$, is of particular interest. In many cases, the prior over \mathbf{x} would imply an inappropriate prior for T . For example, suppose that π is flat over the range $[0, 100]$ for each x_i , and that $T = \frac{1}{n} \sum_i x_i$. By the central limit theorem, the implied prior for T would be approximately

$$T \sim \text{Normal} \left(50, \left(\frac{100}{\sqrt{12n}} \right)^2 \right), \quad (7)$$

which could be narrow for large n . Of course, in many cases it is appropriate and desirable for certain distributions to be narrow, but here the assumption is that this is an unintended consequence of the naive uniform prior. We revisit this example in Section 4.

To fix this, we could apply a constraint to the *implied marginal distribution of T* , so that it does what we want. To see the resulting MaxEnt distribution, we will now examine a simple case, from which we can infer the general result. Consider a case where $T = f(\mathbf{x})$ could only take values 1, 2, and 3. According to any distribution $p(\mathbf{x})$, The probability that $T = 1$ would be given by

$$P(T = 1) = \int p(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{1}(f(\mathbf{x}) = 1) d\mathbf{x}, \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{1}()$ is an indicator function that returns 1 if the argument is true, and 0 if it is false. Similarly, the probabilities $P(T = 2)$ and $P(T = 3)$ would be

$$P(T = 2) = \int p(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{1}(f(\mathbf{x}) = 2) d\mathbf{x} \quad (9)$$

$$P(T = 3) = \int p(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{1}(f(\mathbf{x}) = 3) d\mathbf{x}. \quad (10)$$

These three values would form the implied probability distribution for T according to $p(\mathbf{x})$. However, the expressions for the three probabilities are also interpretable as expected values (of indicator functions). Therefore, controlling the implied marginal distribution of T is the same as controlling three expected values, and the MaxEnt solution is the canonical distribution:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \propto \pi(\mathbf{x}) \exp(\lambda_1 \mathbf{1}(f(\mathbf{x}) = 1) + \lambda_2 \mathbf{1}(f(\mathbf{x}) = 2) + \lambda_3 \mathbf{1}(f(\mathbf{x}) = 3)). \quad (11)$$

As usual, the λ hyperparameters would have to be chosen so that the desired prior for T is obtained.

Note that the expression inside the exponential is simply a way of expressing a transformed version of T , called the indicator function expansion. If $T = 1$ the function returns λ_1 , if $T = 2$ it returns λ_2 , and if $T = 3$ it returns λ_3 . We can therefore write the result more simply as

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \propto \pi(\mathbf{x}) \exp(g(f(\mathbf{x}))). \quad (12)$$

where $g()$ is a function that needs to be tweaked until the desired marginal distribution of T is achieved. The exponential can be absorbed into the function $g()$, giving the simpler result

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \propto \pi(\mathbf{x})g(f(\mathbf{x})), \quad (13)$$

where the function $g()$ can no longer be negative. While motivated by the simple situation with only three possible values for T , Equation 13 is in fact the general solution for a single derived quantity T .

If there are several such derived quantities T_1, \dots, T_m given by functions $f_1(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_m(\mathbf{x})$, the general expression for the updated probability distribution $p(\mathbf{x})$ becomes

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \propto \pi(\mathbf{x})g(f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x}), \dots, f_m(\mathbf{x})). \quad (14)$$

We are now in a position to show that mixtures of canonical distributions are of the form of Equation 14, and are therefore maximum entropy distributions with a constraint on the marginal distribution of a derived quantity. Let \mathbf{x} be the unknown quantities, and assume that the conditional distributions are canonical distributions:

$$p(\mathbf{x} | \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \frac{\pi(\mathbf{x}) \exp(\sum_i \lambda_i f_i(\mathbf{x}))}{Z(\boldsymbol{\lambda})}. \quad (15)$$

This equation is equivalent to Equation 3 except the dependence on $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is now explicit on the left hand side.

The marginal distribution for \mathbf{x} can be found by assigning a prior for the Lagrange multipliers, and then integrating them out:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \int p(\boldsymbol{\lambda})p(\mathbf{x} | \boldsymbol{\lambda}) d\boldsymbol{\lambda} \quad (16)$$

$$= \int p(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) \frac{\pi(\mathbf{x}) \exp(\sum_i \lambda_i f_i(\mathbf{x}))}{Z(\boldsymbol{\lambda})} d\boldsymbol{\lambda}. \quad (17)$$

We do not need to perform this integral to see that overall, the expression only depends on \mathbf{x} through the functions $\{f_i(\mathbf{x})\}$, which act as ‘sufficient statistics’. The marginal distribution $p(\mathbf{x})$ is therefore of the form of Equation 14, and is a maximum entropy distribution, where the prior was $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ and the constraint for the updating procedure is a specified distribution for the derived quantities $\{f_i(\mathbf{x})\}$. The maximum entropy update applies only on the space of \mathbf{x} (not the joint space of \mathbf{x} and λ), and the Lagrange multiplier hyperparameters can be interpreted as a practical device to make the whole procedure tractable.

We will now examine two elementary examples.

4. EXPONENTIAL EXAMPLE

As a simple example, consider a flat prior π defined between 0 and 100 for some positive quantities $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, \dots, x_n\}$. As discussed previously, the central limit theorem gives (to a good approximation) the implied prior for the arithmetic mean $T = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$. The result is a normal distribution, which might be quite narrow, and this might be an unintended consequence of the uniform distribution rather than a justified conclusion. For example, if $n = 100$ the implied prior for T is

$$T \sim \text{Normal}(50, 2.89^2). \quad (18)$$

If we were to specify a constraint on the expected value of T ,

$$\left\langle \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \right\rangle = \mu, \quad (19)$$

Figure 1: The orange distribution is the implied prior for the log of the arithmetic mean of 100 positive quantities, using a $\text{Uniform}(0, 100)$ distribution. The blue distribution is the implied prior using a hierarchical model with $\log \mu \sim \text{Uniform}(-5, 5)$, expressing more appropriate prior uncertainty about the arithmetic mean.

then assuming that $\mu \ll 100$, the updated distribution via MaxEnt, for this moment constraint, would be a product of independent exponentials:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{\mu} \exp\left(-\frac{x_i}{\mu}\right) \quad (20)$$

$$\propto \mu^{-n} \exp\left(-\frac{nT}{\mu}\right). \quad (21)$$

If we let the constraint value μ be unknown, this is the conditional distribution $p(\mathbf{x} | \mu)$ only. However, we can find the marginal distribution by integrating out μ :

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \int_0^{\infty} p(\mu) \mu^{-n} \exp\left(-\frac{nT}{\mu}\right) d\mu. \quad (22)$$

This is of the form of Equation 13, since the integral depends on \mathbf{x} only through T . Therefore, this is a maximum entropy distribution for \mathbf{x} with a constraint on the marginal distribution of T .

This argument implies that applying MaxEnt with a moment constraint to obtain a conditional distribution, then applying a prior over the hyperparameter in the conditional distribution, is equivalent to applying MaxEnt with a constraint on the *marginal distribution* of T .

The difficulty with this approach is that it is hard to find the function $g()$ that would lead to a particular marginal distribution of T . By using the hierarchical route, we are indirectly controlling the prior for T by choosing the prior for the hyperparameter μ . Hopefully, for some choice of prior $p(\mu)$, we can obtain an acceptable prior over T , and in doing so, we will end up with a distribution over \mathbf{x} that is a maximum entropy distribution.

In this specific example, a common choice would be to use a log-uniform prior for the hyperparameter μ . For example, if we use $\log \mu \sim \text{Uniform}(-5, 5)$, Figure 1 shows the resulting implied prior distribution for T , which is close enough to log-uniform for practical purposes.

5. GAUSSIAN EXAMPLE

Consider n values x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n which may be positive or negative. Let the prior $\pi(\mathbf{x})$ be flat over a very wide range. Suppose that we are interested in the following two quantities derived from \mathbf{x} :

$$T_1 = f_1(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \quad (23)$$

$$T_2 = f_2(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2. \quad (24)$$

If we fixed the expected values of T_1 and T_2 , the maximum entropy distribution is:

$$p(\mathbf{x}) \propto \exp \left(\lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \lambda_2 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \right) \quad (25)$$

$$= \exp \left(\sum_{i=1}^n [\lambda_1 x_i + \lambda_2 x_i^2] \right), \quad (26)$$

which is a product of n ‘iid’ normal distributions and may also be written as

$$p(\mathbf{x} | \mu, \sigma) \propto \prod_{i=1}^n \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} (x_i - \mu)^2 \right), \quad (27)$$

where the more traditional hyperparameters μ and σ replace the Lagrange multipliers λ_1 and λ_2 .

A hierarchical model can be constructed if we act as if μ and σ are unknown, but have a prior $p(\mu, \sigma)$. The resulting marginal distribution over \mathbf{x} would then be given by

$$p(\mathbf{x}) = \int p(\mu, \sigma) p(\mathbf{x} | \mu, \sigma) d\mu d\sigma \quad (28)$$

$$\propto \int p(\mu, \sigma) \prod_{i=1}^n \exp \left(-\frac{1}{2\sigma^2} (x_i - \mu)^2 \right) d\mu d\sigma \quad (29)$$

$$= \int p(\mu, \sigma) \exp \left(\lambda_1 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i + \lambda_2 \sum_{i=1}^n x_i^2 \right) d\mu d\sigma. \quad (30)$$

Since the entire expression on the right depends on the \mathbf{x} quantities only through the ‘sufficient statistics’ T_1 and T_2 , this marginal prior over \mathbf{x} is of the form of Equation 14. Therefore, by going through this procedure, we have obtained a MaxEnt distribution over \mathbf{x} . Figure 2 shows an example of the implied prior for the sum and sum of squares of the x quantities from the uniform prior and the hierarchical model.

6. CONCLUSION

The maximum entropy principle is often applied to expected value or moment constraints, yielding the canonical distribution as the result. However, this only applies if we somehow obtain precise values for the fixed expectations. If we do not have such precise values, a common procedure is to let the canonical distribution be the *conditional* prior which depends on the unknown values of the Lagrange multipliers (or their equivalent hyperparameters). A prior for these hyperparameters completes the model specification. This is the foundation of ‘maximum entropy on the mean’ [7] approach to inverse problems and ‘superstatistics’ in statistical mechanics [8].

This procedure leads to a particular marginal prior for the original quantities \mathbf{x} which is *not* a canonical distribution, but is a mixture of canonical distributions. It might seem that the maximum entropy interpretation has been lost, but this is not the case. In this contribution, I have demonstrated that the resulting marginal prior for \mathbf{x} is a MaxEnt distribution where the implicit constraint is on the marginal prior for the derived quantities whose expected values were originally fixed.

Figure 2: The orange distribution is the implied prior for the sum and sum of squares of 100 quantities with independent $\text{Uniform}(-100, 100)$ priors. The blue distribution is the implied prior using a hierarchical model, expressing more appropriate prior uncertainty (approximately uniform in the horizontal direction and log-uniform vertically) about the sum and the sum of squares. The U-shape arises from the prior bounds for the hyperparameters. For completeness, these priors were $\mu \sim \text{Uniform}(-100, 100)$ and $\ln \sigma \sim \text{Uniform}(-5, 5)$ independently.

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